

ANIMATION SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SKILLS AND TALENT OF SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7812720>

Annotation: In this article, there is detailed information about the ability of people, the age of the person, the thinking activity of people, the beliefs of nature, society, humanity in the worldview of the person, scientific views, and the animated characteristics of the development of the ability and talent of schoolchildren. information is provided.

Keywords: student, school, person, ability, age, nature, society, culture, development.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлена подробная информация о способностях людей, возрасте человека, мыслительной деятельности людей, воззрениях природы, общества, человечества в мировоззрении человека, научных взглядах, одушевленных характеристиках. развития способностей и талантов школьников.

Ключевые слова: ученик, школа, человек, способности, возраст, природа, общество, культура, развитие.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada insonlarning qobiliyat, shaxsning yosh davri, insonlarning fikrlash faoliyati, shaxsning dunyoqarashidagi tabiat, jamiyat, insoniyatga bo'lgan e'tiqodlari, ilmiy qarashlari va maktab o'quvchilarining qobiliyat va iqtidor rivojlanishining animatsion o'ziga xos xususiyatlari haqida batafsil ma'lumot berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: o'quvchi, maktab, shaxs, qobiliyat, yosh, tabiat, jamiyat, madaniyat, taraqqiyot.

Adolescence is the most complex and at the same time important developmental stage in the work of the youth of a person. Early adolescence includes 11-13 years old, senior adolescence includes 14-16 years old. The most important feature of this period is that it is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood, from youth to maturity.

Adolescence is characterized by intensity and unevenness in the development of the organism. During this period, intensive development of the body and hardening of bones occurs. There is also an irregularity in the activity of the heart and blood vessels, which also causes changes in the verb and sometimes causes discomfort. These, of course, have an effect on the nervous system, and the child quickly becomes irritable.

The main factor determining the physical development of a teenager is puberty, which determines not only the mental, but also the functioning of the working organs.[1]

These dialectical contradictions take place between the forms of reflecting the external world, which have become stabilized and stereotyped with increasing physical, mental and moral capabilities.

Since this development takes place in the educational process, properly organized educational activities affect the balance of the child's psyche and create a basis for his distraction from various thoughts. Attention, memory, thinking processes develop especially during this period. At this time, the child tends to think independently. Therefore, during this period, he tries to observe more in the world of his thoughts, to know the universe and its secrets, and to increase theoretical knowledge. The reason for this is the transition to that age, and the child has a special feeling of "adulthood", which is also expressed in his speech and thinking. That is why the independence provided in education and the well-organized learning conditions, friendly environment can increase the opportunities for independent thinking and develop creative thinking in him. In this way, a teenager's own philosophy, own policy, happiness and love formula are created. Learning to think logically forces him to perform mental operations on his own, to act in the world of concepts and formulas. This leads to the formation of a kind of adolescent egocentrism - the idea that the whole world and its laws should be subordinated to him. That is why children quarrel with their parents during adolescence.

Thinking activity rises to a higher level of generalization and abstraction, consciously understands the causal connections of events, develops criticality. Here, the interests of the teenager are a sensitive period for the growth of abilities. Interests that begin to appear in teenagers are determined when choosing a certain club, and during training in the clubs, these interests grow and strengthen, take on a more stable tone.

Of course, properly organized educational activities will increase the interests of teenagers. Any academic subject and any knowledge is interesting. In order to create interest in teenagers and maintain its stability, first of all, the lessons taught should be bright and lively, non-traditional lessons should be properly organized, modern technologies should be used, and innovative technologies and interactive methods should be used to practice them. It is of great importance to connect, and then to justify the importance of studied subjects in various spheres of life on a correct, scientific basis.[2]

During adolescence, along with the strengthening of interest in science, a stable interest in the future profession begins to form. Despite the wide range of interests, every teenager has a talent for certain activities. This ability cannot be perfected outside of education and work. Often, a teenager overestimates his abilities, while others distrust his strength, will and ability. However, despite this, the teenager strives to be recognized by equals no matter what. If an innocent teenager is rejected by his peers and adults for some reason during this period, he looks at it as a very big terrible event, his interests begin to fade and may even disappear. The most reliable and useful way to prevent difficulties in such a period is to achieve his constant interest in something, to make the motives of activity more meaningful. Independent thinking should not be allowed. For example, in this period, it is pedagogically important to create the conditions to satisfy the interest of a teenager who is interested in technology, to ensure that he does not remain idle, to encourage his every action, to treat him as a person who can do something. Knowing his interests and setting new goals for him is the basis for the formation of the child's abilities. Only then will his ideas about himself be positive, his self-esteem will be fair, his hidden talents will come to the surface, and his ability to do something will be revealed.[3]

The personality of adolescent boys and girls is determined under the influence of the new environment in the society, community, and system of social relations in which they begin to occupy a place.

The main type of activity during adolescence is learning, education, and production work. In this process, characteristic changes occur in the mental development of teenage boys and girls, the conscious attitude to work and learning increases, and the knowledge, skills and skills acquired in the future work activities are used for full participation in it consciousness is formed as one of the necessary conditions.

The development of thinking is a factor in the formation of theoretical thinking, knowledge of the general laws of nature and society, and the formation of the ability to master philosophical categories.[4]

One of the main characteristics of mental development in adolescence is the formation of a worldview, as well as the development of creativity in various fields of knowledge and various types of activity.

Adolescence is characterized by the richness and variety of emotional and emotional relationships to various aspects of life.

Special importance is given to activity in the analysis of characteristics of adolescence.

Activity refers to a set of actions aimed at satisfying human needs and interests. Sociologists study the activity and divide it into the following main groups: social character, goal orientation, planning, continuity.[5]

The social character of the activities of adolescents is that during this period, they absorb and improve all the knowledge gained in the process of social work and historical development of society with their own efforts.

The appropriateness of the activity means that its main goal is a conscious and regular effort to acquire professional qualifications and skills.

And the planning of the activity, all the efforts in this period have such a system that they are interconnected, located in a certain order, according to the basis of the plan. Continuity of activity consists of continuous preparation for professional activity based on a certain time schedule.

The development of self-awareness in adolescents begins with the understanding of personal behavior and ends with the knowledge of moral qualities, character, intellectual capabilities and abilities. As a teenager matures, new qualities and qualities begin to appear in his mental world.

So, in a teenager, the ability is formed in the process of the emergence of skills and qualifications.[6]

Any skill is complex, and it makes different demands on a teenager. If the system of personal characteristics can meet these requirements, the teenager can demonstrate his ability to successfully perform the activity.

So, the needs of adolescence are always growing.

They cover not only educational activities, but also spiritual and material life.

A person's worldview is a system created on the basis of his beliefs and scientific views on nature, society, humanity. The worldview is determined by the inner state of a person, life goals, interests, relationships, positions held.

Adolescence is an important period in the formation of a person.

The new conditions of the life and work of teenage boys and girls, their active educational, social and labor activities have an impact on the formation of the future specialist personality.

The formation of positive qualities in a person creates the basis for the emergence of his abilities.

In our opinion, in the process of interaction with students, the pedagogue must take into account their value system, self-vocation and level of consciousness.

As long as a person is not based on high values and goals, he does not realize the importance of the processes of developing his professional skills and personal qualities.

Professor According to U. Nishonaliev, it is possible to imagine universal positive qualities with proper upbringing as six-faceted.

These are: First, the general characteristics of a person: cuteness, good looks, attractiveness, politeness, development, respectability, seriousness, etc.

Secondly, the moral qualities of a person: humanity, care, sincerity, childishness, compassion, etc.

Thirdly, business qualities: diligence, diligence, responsibility, honesty, perseverance, diligence, etc.

Fourthly, the qualities of intelligence, perceptiveness: intelligence, calmness, prudence, sensitivity, resourcefulness, curiosity, courage, etc.

Fifth, the qualities of stability: activity, determination, quickness, enthusiasm, stability, discipline, stability, perseverance, etc.

Sixth, the qualities of passion: optimism, cheerfulness, cheerfulness, confidence, faith in the future, shyness, chastity, etc.

The formation of the above-mentioned personal qualities is the main task of educational work. All countries try to form these positive qualities in their people. In this sense, the general goal of education is focused on a single goal in the world pedagogical process - the formation of universal human qualities.[7]

Usually, focusing only on one, most important characteristic of a person with special characteristics does not allow to achieve the desired goal. For this reason, it is necessary to focus on increasing the weight of the required characteristics, looking at the activity indicators of the adolescent in all areas as a general set. Having analyzed the abilities of teenagers to solve the task, we found that talented teenagers have the following qualities:

- skill in solving problems;
- high level of logical thinking;
- easy acceptance of knowledge and skills;
- to express his opinion correctly and in detail;
- ability to distribute attention more widely;
- present responsibility;
- able to analyze the problem analytically;
- ingenuity;
- fluency of speech;
- curiosity;
- bring the work to the end;
- adaptability of thinking, etc.

One of the main factors of social development is the development of science and technology, and on its basis, the level of professional training and the appropriateness of this professional training to their personal qualities is the main factor in solving this problem. This problem is directly related to the reform of the education system and the quality of personnel training.[8]

Conclusion. Every graduate of the school, which is considered the main link of the educational system for young people to fully demonstrate their opportunities and abilities, knowledge and intellectual potential, and to use them appropriately in social life should make the right choice and determine the future path of education. In this process, in the formation of a person as a qualified specialist in his field, his personal qualities are of primary importance. Personal qualities are formed in the process of socialization in the family and continuous education system after the birth of an individual.

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